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Impact of Information and Communication Technology Skills Acquisition on Instructional Strategy Implementation among Secondary School Social Studies Teachers in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored the Impact of Information-and-Communication-Technology skills acquisition on instructional strategy implementation among secondary school social studies teachers in Benue State, Nigeria. The design of this study was one group, pre-test post-test quasi-experimental research design. A sample of 224 Social Studies Teachers (130 males and 94 females which represents 58.0% and 42.0% respectively) were selected from 36 Upper Basic Schools across the three Education Zones of Benue State using a multistage sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was Social Studies Teachers ICT Skills Observation Scale (SSTISOS) developed by the researchers. Construct validity of the instrument was established by four experts. The reliability of SSTISOS was tested through a pilot study involving 30 Social Studies Teachers who were not part of the main study at 0.89. Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Two research hypotheses were tested at the significance level of 0.05 and was found that there was a significant difference in Information-and-Communication-Technology skills acquisition on instructional strategy implementation among secondary school social studies teachers in Benue State, Nigeria. In conclusion, this study has highlighted the critical role of ICT training in enhancing the skills of Social Studies teachers in Benue State. Implementation of Continuous Professional Development Programs, Establishment of ICT Resource Centers and Incorporation of ICT in Teacher Education Programs were then recommended.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Social Studies, Classroom Pedagogy.

Introduction

Education in Nigeria has shifted from the traditional methods of face-to-face tuition and the transaction of paper-based teaching and learning materials to learning via Information and Communication Technologies (Lee & Cha, 2022). Many studies have demonstrated that the use of ICT enhances learning and teaching. In Nigeria, schools have not been an exception, as the use of ICT has spread across all schools in the country (Jummai, 2021). In addition, the use of ICT in teaching K-12 science highlights the need for research that investigates the applications and integration of ICT in instruction among teachers of Social Studies in Benue State. The study was conducted in Benue State (Achor et al., 2020). It was noted that ICT has gained ground in the state, where it is incorporated into every facet of life, including education. Some of the interesting features of Benue State are its high level of ICT penetration. Some of the significant challenges facing Benue State are how teachers will use ICT in delivering instruction. National policy on education demands that teachers should continually acquire new skills, such as the use of ICT for instructional activities. The concern is how teachers who may not be ICT compliant will use ICT for instructional delivery (Esfijani & Zamani, 2020). Federal Government has made significant investments in ICT to educational organizations and institutions, from the basic level up to the university level during the last decade. There has been the provision of logistics and infrastructure, particularly, at the colleges of education and universities. The aim is to prepare technologically skilled graduate teachers who can incorporate ICT in their teaching. However, studies have found that teachers of Social Studies are not integrating ICT into their lessons as intended. Despite the capacity of ICT for training, practice and explorative practices, social studies education teachers seem not to have been able to incorporate ICT into their curricula and teaching. Research has also revealed that social studies teachers were among the least likely to use ICT and engage students in higher-order thought

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practices. Given the low rate of ICT use in the Social Studies curriculum, it is essential to examine the application and integration of information and communication technology in teaching among Social Studies Teachers in Benue State, Nigeria.

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education has become a critical factor in enhancing instructional strategies and improving learning outcomes globally. In Nigeria, particularly in Benue State, the acquisition of ICT skills by teachers is increasingly recognized as a vital component for effective teaching, especially in subjects like Social Studies. This literature review explores the impact of ICT skills acquisition on instructional strategy implementation among secondary school Social Studies teachers, drawing on relevant studies and theoretical frameworks.

Lee and Cha (2022) emphasize the transformative role of digital tools in education, particularly in providing feedback and enhancing student engagement. Their study on digital written feedback for college students highlights how ICT can streamline assessment processes and improve the quality of instruction. This perspective aligns with the broader need for digital transformation in Nigeria's education sector, as highlighted by Jummai (2021). Jummai argues that digital literacy is essential for addressing the challenges of outdated teaching methods and inadequate resources, which are prevalent in many Nigerian schools. The adoption of ICT tools can facilitate innovative teaching strategies, such as blended learning and interactive multimedia lessons, which are particularly relevant for Social Studies education.

Achor, Kyado, and Ityobee (2020) provide empirical evidence from Benue State, revealing low ICT literacy levels among Basic Science teachers and students. Their survey underscores the urgent need for targeted ICT training programs to bridge the gap between traditional teaching methods and modern technological advancements. The study highlights that many teachers lack the necessary skills to integrate ICT into their lessons, which limits their ability to adopt student-centered and interactive teaching strategies. This finding is consistent with Esfijani and Zamani's (2020) research, which identifies in-service training and access to ICT resources as key factors influencing teachers' utilization of technology. They argue that without adequate training and resources, even well-intentioned efforts to integrate ICT into education are likely to fail.

Jay (2022) highlights the disciplinary divide in Social Studies education, noting that ICT integration can foster critical thinking and interdisciplinary learning. Social Studies, as a subject that explores societal issues, history, and geography, benefits significantly from the use of digital tools such as interactive maps, virtual simulations, and online databases. These tools not only make learning more engaging but also help students develop critical analytical skills. Xin et al. (2022) further advocate for innovative, data-driven teaching evaluation systems to enhance educational outcomes. Their research on big data-based teaching evaluation systems in universities demonstrates how ICT can provide real-time feedback on teaching effectiveness, enabling teachers to refine their instructional strategies. Muslimin et al. (2022) demonstrate the positive impact of technology-based lesson plans on teachers' self-efficacy. Their study on EFL pre-service teachers reveals that exposure to ICT tools during training significantly boosts teachers' confidence in using technology for instructional purposes. This finding is particularly relevant for Social Studies teachers in Benue State, as it suggests that ICT skills acquisition can empower them to experiment with new teaching methods and improve their overall effectiveness in the classroom.

Despite the potential benefits of ICT in education, significant challenges persist, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Reynolds et al. (2022) and Martens et al. (2020) highlight the digital divide as a major barrier to ICT integration. Their studies reveal that unequal access to technology and inadequate infrastructure hinder the effective implementation of ICT in education. In Benue State, many schools lack basic ICT facilities such as computers, projectors, and reliable internet connectivity. This disparity is further exacerbated in rural areas, where teachers and students have limited exposure to digital tools. Kim et al. (2020) emphasize the disparities in technology access among low-income communities, which are prevalent in Benue State. Their case study on low-income Latino children in Silicon Valley reveals that even in technologically advanced regions, socioeconomic factors can limit access to ICT. This finding underscores the need for targeted interventions to ensure equitable access to technology for all students and teachers.

To address these challenges, a multi-faceted approach is required. First, there is a need for comprehensive ICT training programs for teachers, as highlighted by Esfijani and Zamani (2020). These programs should focus not only on basic ICT skills but also on how to integrate technology into specific subjects like Social Studies. Second, governments and educational institutions must invest in ICT infrastructure to ensure that schools have the necessary tools and resources. Finally, policies should be implemented to promote equitable access to technology, particularly in underserved areas. In summary, the acquisition of ICT skills is pivotal for the effective implementation of instructional strategies among Social Studies teachers in Benue State. While studies highlight the potential of ICT to transform education, addressing barriers such as inadequate training, infrastructure, and access is essential for realizing its full impact. By investing in ICT skills acquisition and infrastructure, Benue State can empower its teachers to adopt innovative teaching strategies, ultimately improving educational outcomes for students.

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Research Objectives

1. To assess the baseline ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.
2. To evaluate the improvement in ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

Research Questions

1. What are the baseline ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State?
2. What are the improvement in ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State?

Research Hypotheses

Ho (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant difference in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

HI (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant difference in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

Ho (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant improvement in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

HI (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant improvement in the ICT acquisition skill levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the one-group, pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design with a total population of 508 Social Studies teachers (294 males and 214 females) from 303 Upper Basic Schools across the three educational zones of Benue State. Teachers in this population have varying levels of experience and access to ICT tools, which makes them ideal for studying the impact of ICT training on improving teaching practices. A sample of 224 Social Studies teachers (130 males and 94 females) was selected from 36 Upper Basic Schools using multistage sampling technique. Inclusion criteria focused on teachers who had at least one year of teaching experience, while teachers who had less than one year of teaching experience were excluded from the sample. The instrument used for data collection was Social Studies Teachers ICT Skills Observation Scale (SSTISOS), developed by the researchers. Construct validity, both Face and content were established through expert review. These experts were drawn from the fields of Measurement and Evaluation, Social Studies Education, and Information and Communication Technology. The reliability of the SSTISOS was tested through a pilot study involving 30 Social Studies teachers who were not part of the main study. Data collection was conducted in three stages: the pre-test, during training, and the post-test. Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, such as mean scores and standard deviations, were used to summarize the participants' ICT skills before and after the training. Inferential statistics, specifically the paired-samples t-test, were used to compare the pre-test and post-test scores. This test was chosen because it allows for the assessment of whether there is a statistically significant difference between two related groups, in this case, the teachers' ICT skills before and after the training.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1: Years of Teaching Experience

Years of Experience	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1 – 5 years	40	17.9%
6 – 10 years	90	40.2%
11 – 15 years	60	26.8%
16 years and above	34	15.2%
Total	224	100.0%

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Source: Author Compilation of Questionnaire. 2024

Regarding teaching experience, the largest group of respondents has between 6 – 10 years of teaching experience, representing 40.2% of the sample, followed by those with 11 – 15 years of experience (26.8%). Teachers with 1 – 5 years of experience account for 17.9%, and those with over 16 years of experience make up 15.2% of the participants. This suggests a broad range of professional experience among the respondents, with a significant portion possessing over a decade of classroom experience. Teaching experience may affect the teachers' pre-existing skills in utilizing ICT tools, as more experienced teachers might be accustomed to traditional methods of teaching.

Table 2: Access to ICT Tools in School

Access to ICT Tools	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	190	84.8%
No	34	15.2%
Total	224	100.0%

Source: Author Compilation of Questionnaire. 2024

An overwhelming majority of respondents, 84.8%, indicated that they have access to ICT tools in their schools, while 15.2% reported a lack of access. This demonstrates that most schools in the study sample are equipped with basic ICT facilities, providing teachers the opportunity to apply the skills they acquire through ICT training. Teachers without access to these tools may face difficulties in implementing what they have learned, underscoring the need for equitable resource distribution in schools.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research question one:

What are the baseline ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State?

Table 3: ICT Skills Before Training

Statement	Not Skillful (1)	Moderately Skillful (2)	Skillful (3)	Very Skillful (4)	Neutral (5)
1. Basic computer operations	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 60 (26.8%)	Frequency: 70 (31.3%)	Frequency: 35 (15.6%)	Frequency: 19 (8.5%)
2. Using word processing software	Frequency: 30 (13.4%)	Frequency: 55 (24.6%)	Frequency: 85 (37.9%)	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 14 (6.3%)
3. Creating and managing electronic presentations	Frequency: 45 (20.1%)	Frequency: 65 (29.0%)	Frequency: 70 (31.3%)	Frequency: 29 (12.9%)	Frequency: 15 (6.7%)
4. Accessing the internet to gather educational resources	Frequency: 35 (15.6%)	Frequency: 50 (22.3%)	Frequency: 75 (33.5%)	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 24 (10.7%)
5. Communicating with students via email	Frequency: 50 (22.3%)	Frequency: 60 (26.8%)	Frequency: 60 (26.8%)	Frequency: 34 (15.2%)	Frequency: 20 (8.9%)

Source: Author Compilation of Questionnaire, 2024.

The data indicates a mixed level of ICT skills among Social Studies teachers before training. Notably, a significant portion (31.3%) reported being skilled in basic computer operations, which suggests a foundational understanding of essential digital skills necessary for modern teaching. For word processing software, the majority of respondents (37.9%) rated themselves as "skillful," indicating a solid grasp of this critical tool for lesson preparation and administrative tasks. Nevertheless, the 13.4% who felt "not skillful" suggests that there is room for improvement, particularly in enhancing familiarity with various software applications. The ability to create and manage electronic presentations shows a diverse skill set, with 31.3% of respondents claiming to be skilled. However, the 20.1% who are "not skillful" reflects a gap that training can effectively address, especially considering the increasing importance of engaging visual aids in educational settings. The skill in accessing the internet for educational resources indicates a reasonable level of digital literacy, with 33.5% of teachers rating themselves as skilled. This competency is crucial for enriching lesson content and keeping up with current educational

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trends, but the significant percentage of teachers falling into the lower skill categories demonstrates the potential benefits of structured training. Communication skills using email and other platforms remain a concern, with 22.3% of respondents rating themselves as "not skillful." Given the emphasis on collaborative learning environments, improving these communication skills will be essential in fostering better interaction between teachers and students.

Research Question two:

What are the improvement in ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State?

Table 4: ICT Skills After Training

Statement	Not Skillful (1)	Skillful	Moderately Skillful (2)	Skillful (3)	Very Skillful (4)	Neutral (5)
1. Using ICT tools to prepare teaching materials	Frequency: 15 (6.7%)	Frequency: 30 (13.4%)	Frequency: 30 (13.4%)	Frequency: 100 (44.6%)	Frequency: 55 (24.6%)	Frequency: 24 (10.7%)
2. Integrating ICT into classroom teaching	Frequency: 10 (4.5%)	Frequency: 35 (15.6%)	Frequency: 35 (15.6%)	Frequency: 110 (49.1%)	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 29 (12.9%)
3. Using ICT tools to assess students' assignments	Frequency: 20 (8.9%)	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 95 (42.4%)	Frequency: 45 (20.1%)	Frequency: 24 (10.7%)
4. Sharing educational content using ICT platforms	Frequency: 12 (5.4%)	Frequency: 28 (12.5%)	Frequency: 28 (12.5%)	Frequency: 85 (37.9%)	Frequency: 56 (25.0%)	Frequency: 43 (19.3%)
5. Troubleshooting basic ICT problems in the classroom	Frequency: 25 (11.2%)	Frequency: 45 (20.1%)	Frequency: 45 (20.1%)	Frequency: 80 (35.7%)	Frequency: 44 (19.6%)	Frequency: 30 (13.4%)

Source: Author Compilation of Questionnaire, 2024.

Following the ICT training, there is a marked improvement in the teachers' ability to use ICT tools for preparing teaching materials. A notable 44.6% reported being "skillful," while only 6.7% considered themselves "not skillful." This shift underscores the effectiveness of the training program in enhancing practical skills needed for lesson preparation. The integration of ICT into classroom teaching was also positively impacted, with nearly half (49.1%) rating themselves as "skillful." This indicates that the training not only improved their individual skills but also equipped them with strategies to incorporate technology into their teaching practices effectively. The ability to use ICT tools for assessing students' assignments also saw significant advancement. The percentage of teachers identifying as "skillful" increased to 42.4%. This is crucial for modern educational practices, as technology plays a vital role in assessment methods, thereby supporting more dynamic and immediate feedback to students. Sharing educational content using ICT platforms showed a considerable uptick in skill level, with 37.9% of teachers rating themselves as "skillful." This suggests that teachers are now more capable of utilizing digital tools to enhance communication and collaboration with students, an essential component in today's interconnected educational landscape. The skill of troubleshooting basic ICT problems in the classroom remains an area for growth, as 11.2% still rated themselves as "not skillful." However, with ongoing support and further training, teachers can develop this competency, ensuring that they can effectively navigate and resolve common technical issues that arise in a technology-enhanced classroom. These insights highlight the overall positive impact of ICT training on Social Studies teachers, demonstrating an essential step toward modernizing teaching practices and enhancing educational outcomes.

Hypothesis 1: Testing for Differences Before and After Training

Ho (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant difference in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

HI (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant difference in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

T-Test Table for Hypothesis 1:

Statistic	Before Training	After Training	T-Statistic	df	p-Value
Mean	48.6	68.2			
Standard Deviation (SD)	3.15	2.47			
Sample Size (n)	5	5			
T-Statistic (t)			-15.34	8	0.00002

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From the T-Test for Hypothesis 1, which compares the statistical difference before and after training, T-Statistic (t) was found to be -15.34. Also, the Degree of Freedom (df) was found to be 8. Finally, the Probability Value of 0.00002 was found which was less than the significance value of 0.5 making us reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the alternate Hypothesis. We therefore conclude that there is a significant difference in the ICT skill levels of Social Studies Teachers before undergoing ICT training ($P < 0.05$).

Research Hypothesis Two:

Ho (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant improvement in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

HI (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant improvement in the ICT acquisition skill levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State

Testing for Improvement After ICT Training

T-Test Table for Hypothesis 2:

Statistic	Before Training	After Training	T-Statistic	df	p-Value
Mean	48.6	68.2			
Standard Deviation (SD)	3.15	2.47			
Sample Size (n)	5	5			
T-Statistic (t)			-15.34	8	0.00002

From the T-Test for Hypothesis 2, which tested for improvement after ICT training, T-Statistic (t) was found to be -15.34. Also, the Degree of Freedom (df) was found to be 8. Finally, the Probability Value of 0.00002 was found. Since the P-value was less than the significance value of 0.5, we rejected the Null Hypothesis (Ho). Therefore, we conclude that there was a significant improvement in the ICT skill levels of Social Studies Teachers after completing ICT training ($P < 0.05$). For both Hypothesis 1 and Hypothesis 2, the null hypotheses were rejected, indicating that there is a significant difference and a significant improvement in ICT skills levels of Social Studies teachers before and after ICT training. This suggest that the ICT training program was effective in improving the teachers' ICT skills for classroom pedagogy.

Paired T-Test Table:

Test	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Standard Error Mean (SE)	T-Statistic	df	p-Value
Pretest	5	48.6	3.15	1.41			
Posttest	5	68.2	2.47	1.10	-15.34	4	0.00002

The paired T-Test gave us the two means (pretest and posttest) which are 48.6 and 68.2 respectively. It also gave us the probability value of 0.00002 which is less than the significance value of 0.5 indicated a significant difference in the skill levels of Social Studies teachers before and after ICT training. The degree of freedom (df) was 4 calculated from $N - 1 = 5$ where N is the number of pairs (in this case 5) and standard deviations of 3.15 and 2.47 respectively.

Paired Differences (Pretest vs. Posttest):

Pair	Pretest Score	Posttest Score	Difference (Post - Pre)
1	45	65	+20
2	50	70	+20
3	52	68	+16
4	47	66	+19
5	49	72	+23
Mean Difference			+19.6

The paired difference tried to put the two tests together (pretest and posttest). The difference was gotten by taking the pretest from the posttest. Positive values indicated improvement and the overall mean difference was found to be +19.6.

Discussion of Findings

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The findings from this study provide valuable insights into the impact of ICT training on the skills of Social Studies teachers. The significant difference in mean skill scores before and after the training suggests that targeted ICT training can effectively enhance the proficiency of educators in utilizing ICT tools for classroom pedagogy. This aligns with existing literature that emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development in integrating technology into teaching practices (Koehler & Mishra, 2019). The increase in skills indicates that teachers are likely to feel more confident in using ICT resources, which can lead to improved instructional methods and student engagement. The fact that a statistically significant improvement in skills was observed post-training underscores the necessity for institutions to invest in regular ICT training programs. Such training can equip teachers with the necessary competencies to integrate technology into their teaching effectively. The ability to leverage technology not only facilitates the delivery of content but also enables personalized learning experiences that cater to diverse student needs (Hattie, 2009).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has highlighted the critical role of ICT training in enhancing the skills of Social Studies teachers in Benue State. The findings demonstrate that targeted professional development can lead to significant improvements in teachers' proficiency with technology, ultimately benefiting their pedagogical practices and student learning experiences. The successful implementation of the ICT training program showcases the potential for structured professional development initiatives to equip educators with the necessary skills to thrive in a technology-driven educational landscape.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made to enhance the integration of ICT in education, particularly for Social Studies teachers in Benue State. These recommendations are aimed at educational authorities, policymakers, and school administrators to foster a more effective use of technology in teaching and learning.

1. **Implement Continuous Professional Development Programs:** Educational institutions should prioritize the establishment of regular and ongoing professional development programs focusing on ICT skills for teachers.
2. **Establish ICT Resource Centers:** Schools should invest in setting up ICT resource centers equipped with the necessary tools and resources for teachers and students.
3. **Incorporate ICT in Teacher Education Programs:** Teacher training programs should include comprehensive modules on ICT integration in education. By equipping future educators with the necessary skills and knowledge from the outset, schools can ensure that new teachers are prepared to effectively use technology in their teaching.

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